

INFLUENCE OF EXCESS BODY MASS ON THE CARDIOVASCULAR
SYSTEM IN CHILDREN

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Relevance Excess body mass in children has become a global epidemic, with its prevalence continuously increasing over the past three decades. Timely diagnosis and the improvement of methods for correcting excess body mass and obesity in children should be aimed at preventing the progression of complications, particularly cardiovascular diseases.

Research Objective. To study the characteristics of the cardiovascular system in children with obesity.

Materials and Methods .A comprehensive clinical examination was conducted on 20 children aged 8 to 10 years (8 girls (40%) and 12 boys (60%)) with obesity ranging from Grade I to III. The examination included an assessment of medical history, anthropometric data, and an evaluation of the cardiovascular system (ECG and blood pressure measurement).

Research Findings.According to parental reports, excess weight was observed from the early years of life in 30% of children, from the age of 5 in 50%, and from the age of 7 in 20%. Complaints analysis revealed that excess weight was a concern for 70% of boys and 80% of girls and their parents. Among the reported symptoms, children with Grade II–III obesity most frequently experienced headaches (50%), chest pain

and shortness of breath during physical activity (40%), and palpitations at rest (20% of boys and 30% of girls). Elevated blood pressure (up to $130\pm 0.2 / 90\pm 0.3$ mmHg) was observed in 18% of the children. Children exhibited an abdominal obesity type (80%) with an average BMI of 24.5 ± 0.8 kg/m². Striae (stretch marks) were present in 85% of patients, and autonomic dysfunctions such as acrocyanosis, skin marbling, and excessive sweating of the palms and feet were recorded in 80% of cases. Additional findings included muffled heart sounds (85%), systolic murmur at the apex and at the point of maximal intensity in Botkin's area (80%), and an accentuated second heart sound over the aorta (10%). ECG results revealed sinus rhythm in 50% of children, sinus arrhythmia in 30%, and mild sinus tachycardia in 20%. Intraventricular conduction disturbances were found in 10%, myocardial repolarization disorders in 15%, and metabolic changes in the myocardium in 75% of cases. No stable arterial hypertension was identified based on time index and hypertension index assessments. Correlation analysis established a relationship between systolic and diastolic blood pressure and factors such as height ($r=0.52-0.38$, $p<0.001$), weight ($r=0.48-0.38$, $p<0.001$), and BMI ($r=0.37-0.34$, $p<0.001$). A strong correlation was also found between average systolic blood pressure values and sinus tachycardia ($r=0.46$, $p<0.001$) as well as myocardial repolarization disorders ($r=0.48$, $p<0.001$).

Conclusions. Among the examined children aged 8 to 10 years with obesity, boys outnumbered girls by 1.5 times. Abdominal obesity was present in 80% of the children, and 85% exhibited striae. Autonomic dysfunctions were recorded in 85% of children, characterized by acrocyanosis skin marbling, excessive sweating of the palms and feet (80%), muffled heart sounds (85%), systolic murmur at the apex and in Botkin's area (80%), and an accentuated second heart sound over the aorta (10%). Early structural and geometric changes in the myocardium, a hypersympathicotonic variant of cardiovascular function, a high prevalence of circadian rhythm disturbances in blood pressure, and an increased rate of morning

blood pressure rise were more common with higher obesity grades and longer obesity duration. These factors may serve as triggering mechanisms for the development of cardiovascular complications in the future.